

Supplementary Material

Figure S1: Phylogenetic tree of the 10 fowl species included in the multiple sequence alignment used in the polarisation step. The ancestral sequence reconstructed in cactus that was used to polarise variants into ancestral and derived is indicated by the arrow, whereas the chicken genome used as reference in the study is highlighted in red.

Figure S2: All breeds principal component analysis (PCA). The principal component analysis was performed on all samples, considering as input only bi-allelic SNPs with a missing rate <10% and a minor allele frequency of 0.05 ($n = 12,168,183$ SNPs). We did not perform any linkage disequilibrium (LD) pruning. Barbezieux samples are shown in green, whereas Gasconne samples in purple. Samples belonging to the two different time points (2003 and 2013/15) are identified by different shapes.

Figure S3: Breed-specific principal component analysis (PCA). The principal component analysis was performed on the two breeds separately after filtering for an LD threshold of 0.5. After LD pruning, a total of 65,665 and 88,769 bi-allelic SNPs were retained for the Barbezieux (in green) and Gasconne (in purple) breed, respectively. Samples belonging to the two different time points (2003 and 2013/15) are identified by different shapes.

Figure S4: Neighbour-Joining (NJ) tree. The NJ tree was constructed from the identity-by-state (IBS) distance relationship matrix estimated on 12,476,884 SNPs after filtering for a missing rate <10% and a minor allele frequency (MAF) of 0.05. Barbezieux samples are shown in green, whereas Gasconne samples in purple.

Figure S5: Heterozygosity outside runs of homozygosity (ROH). Heterozygosity is here estimated from regions of the genome that were excluded from the ROH analysis because of their higher-than-expected heterozygosity. Only 10-kb windows with at least 80% of sites meeting our coverage criteria were considered. Barbezieux samples are shown in green, whereas Gasconne samples in purple. In both breeds, changes in heterozygosity outside ROH were not significant.

Figure S6: Number of runs of homozygosity (ROH) per individual for different ROH size classes. The number of ROH in various size classes is indicative of the individual's demographic history. In order, from left to right, short ROH (100 Kb - 1 Mb), medium (1 - 3 Mb) and long (≥ 3 Mb) ROH. Barbezieux samples are shown in green, whereas Gasconne samples in purple.

Figure S7: Total length of runs of homozygosity (ROH) per individual for different ROH size classes. Barbezieux samples are shown in green, whereas Gasconne samples in purple.

Figure S8: Identity-by-descent (IBD) segments. (Top) Total length (in Mb) of shared IBD segments between Barbezieux samples. (Bottom) Total length (in Mb) of shared IBD segments between Gasconne samples. Comparisons between individuals sampled in 2003 are grouped in green, while those between individuals sampled in 2013/15 are in blue. We considered only segments that were at least 100Kb (or 0.1 cM) long for consistency purposes with the ROH analysis (see Materials and methods).

Figure S9: Trend in pedigree-based inbreeding coefficient (F_{ped}). Generation 3 (year 2003) and 13 (year 2013) are highlighted in grey.

Figure S10: Trend in population size. The y-axis shows the total number of sires (green) and dams (blue) per generation (x-axis). Generation 3 (year 2003) and 13 (year 2013) are highlighted in grey.

Figure S11: Derived allele frequency distribution. (Left) Derived allele frequency distribution of protein-coding variants, classified into synonymous, nonsynonymous tolerated (SIFT > 0.05), nonsynonymous putative deleterious (SIFT ≤ 0.05), and nonsynonymous deleterious (SIFT ≤ 0.05; GERP > 1.0). (Right) Derived allele frequency distribution of protein-coding variants classified into benign (synonymous and tolerated missense mutations) and truly damaging (deleterious missense mutations and mutations that disrupt splice sites or start or stop codons).

Figure S12: Temporal changes in allele frequency. a. Allele frequency distribution of the Barbezieux breed in 2003 and 2013. b. Allele frequency distribution of the Gasconne breed in 2003 and 2013.

Figure S13: Body weight at 8 weeks (Pds8s). The graph shows the values of the phenotype *body weight at 8 weeks* averaged among all individuals in each generation, ranging from 2003 to 2019 for the Barbezieux (left) and 2010 to 2015 for the Gasconne (right).